

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. JANETH L. LACOSTALES

Instructor I

Cebu Technological University – Barili Campus

janeth.lacostales@ctu.edu.ph

“APPA AND I”

My name is Anya, I'm fifteen years old. I grew up with my grandmother because my mom has worked in Korea since I was 8 years old. I do have many things I wanted to say to her but I preferred not to. Seeing her struggle due to the fact that she is in a faraway place, I couldn't bear to open up to her about my own struggles. I love my mom so much and I am so proud of her, being able to raise me well, despite not having a husband. Yes, my mom is a solo parent that is why, I couldn't bear to see her struggle, I never want to see her hurt, and I am willing to do everything for her—even if that means, suppressing my own struggles.

I've always been used to this setting, video calls, chats, longings, and ifs. But one day a news broke in and I never knew that, that same news will change our lives forever. My mom married her long-term Korean boyfriend, Kim Joo Hyeok. I knew him, my mom introduced me to him during a video call, but that's it! I never heard from him ever again, and now, they got married? Are they kidding me? Worst is, I have to go to Korea as soon as possible to live there—forever. My mom did not even give me an option. But as I said, I am willing to do everything for her. So, as an obedient child, I followed her.

Just like that, I have set my foot, for the first time in a foreign land. I do not like their language, their culture, not to mention their weather! I came to Korea in uncertainty but, I got to try my luck, right?

As soon as I got to the Incheon Airport Arrivals Hall, I shivered seeing my mom for the first time in seven years. Her beautiful eyes shone brighter than the sun. Her long curly locks that I used to smell and play with hang attractively over her shoulders. “That's my mom,” I said to myself, “I can't believe I am seeing her in person, after seven long and arduous years.”

I ran toward this woman who bear me in her womb for nine months and embraced her like a newborn baby that doesn't want to be separated from her mother ever again. But this surreal moment abruptly ended when I heard a voice that said, “Ann-yeong-ha-se-yo”. I turned to see the owner of that deep, and very manly voice, only to see my mom's husband in person, Kim Joo Hyeok.

Mr. Kim Joo Hyeok's presence may have become a real-life Korean Drama character if I were a fan, but no, I am not, so he looked nothing but ordinary to me. I neither can speak their language nor understand it, so I just looked at him coldly from head to foot, and drew my attention back to my mom. Mr. Joo Hyeok drove us to his home where my mom also lives now. I believe he has perceived that there is a language barrier between us that is why he never even dared to talk to me or greet me again but I think he does not dislike my presence.

Observant as I am, I observed this man. He carried all my luggage without being asked, he opened the door for me, welcomed me to their living room with a smile, and even prepared food for me. I was even more surprised when my

mom secretly told me that even before my arrival, he has constantly asked about foods that I like. That being said, my eyes grew wide when I saw “tinolang manok” being served in a Korean table. Plus, the taste doesn’t feel Korean at all! He purposely cooked it in the Filipino way, not to impress me with his skills as a chef, but to show me that he is glad I arrived safely. It is then that I slowly figured out why my mom decided to marry him. “He is a good man,” I said to myself.

That night, I brought myself to sleep with a smile on my face. I think, I will be able to cope up with their culture, and learn their language. I need to try, after all, my not-so-familiar dad also tried.

Morning came in just a blink of an eye. “Good morning sleepy head,” I heard my mom say as I went out of my room, “breakfast is ready!”

When I went to the kitchen, my jaw dropped, seeing all of my favorite Filipino dishes being served at the table. “Is... is it my birthday?” I asked in confusion.

“No, child! Does it have to be your birthday?” answered mom.

“No.” I replied as I started munching all my favorite food all at once!

At the back of my mind, I realized, this man is no ordinary. All this shows his affection, not just for my mom, but also for me. I am going to open my heart and mind. I will give this man a chance.

Thus, without any more hesitations, I studied Hangeul, the Korean language, from its letters to its sounds. I even learned to read words in just a day! As time went by, I grew even more interested in their language, and then I started learning about their culture—when to use honorifics, what is rude and what’s not, and all.

The home that seemed like an alien to me is now starting to feel like a real home. One morning, I woke up early in order to have a chance to say, “Kam-sa-ham-ni-da”, to Mr. Joo Hyeok. I figured, just have to do it, seeing how much he values our Filipino culture. Then, upon hearing my stuttering Korean, Mr. Joo Hyeok replied, “A-ni, no-nuhn, u-ri ttal-i-yeyo.” Which means, “You do not have to thank me, you are our daughter.”

His words did not just make me cry, I did not even hesitate to hug him tight because for the longest time, I have wanted to have a father and now, this man took courage to take me as his daughter and to show me the love that even my own father failed to give me. This is the time that I realized, cultures and languages may not be the main reason for miscommunication, it may be the heart. We need to open our heart first to foreign cultures and languages. We do not need to actually master their culture or speak their language, all we have to do is show them the love and respect they needed and I believe, they will do same. Believe me, it works! It’s the reason why Appa and I became close and learned to love each other despite our differences.